

Entrepreneurial Intentions of the Graduating Students in Oman: A Case Study - Sohar university

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Abstract

Purpose of the study: The objective of the study is to critically do a review of literature on the factors impacting the entrepreneurial intention of the graduating students and to critically analyze the impact of such factors on the entrepreneurial intention of the graduating students.

Design/Methodology: 269 undergraduate students were selected on a random sampling basis from Sohar University and were considered to be the sample for the study. An online questionnaire was shared through digital media for survey purposes which were filled by students. The statistical analysis was carried out using excel and SPSS.

Findings: The findings of the study reveal that the Entrepreneurial intention is influenced by Graduate Potentials, Creativity, and Education of the students and not by Government support. The undergraduate students are developing creative skills and bringing out their entrepreneurial potentials and improvising their practical knowledge through their education.

Implications: It was suggested that the graduating students need proper guidance to fulfill their entrepreneurial intention which is in the hands of teachers. Students should be exposed to the development of various skills – creativity, communication, presentation, marketing, funds management, etc. and they should be invited to a platform where competitions of all innovative kinds should be conducted regularly and the participants should be guided with assistance to improve their ideas.

Originality: This research work is one of its first kind as no study was conducted before focusing on the entrepreneurial intentions of the students in Oman.

Keywords: *Entrepreneurial Intention, Entrepreneurial Potentials, Creativity, Government support, Education.*

Introduction

Entrepreneurship is the process of creating a new business that has not previously existed or developing a business with the opportunities available to develop and advance innovatively (Santarelli & Vivarelli, 2007). The fact that entrepreneurship fulfils the dream of the owner of an entrepreneurial idea to apply it on the field, and thus constitutes a new source of jobs to the labour market and source of income to improve the living condition. Also, it aims to develop and support a specific project that would raise the level of economic and technological performance of the country. Entrepreneurship is recognized as an important source of job growth and economic development for a country and is not limited to megaprojects but rather small projects that include small companies with limited responsibility, in-country value projects, and petty commercial businesses (Audretsch & Thurik, 2001).

Entrepreneurs are considered as crucial growth agents of a nation to achieve economic, social, technological and organizational development and they serve as catalysts for economic development due to the wide array of economic benefits provided by them in terms of introducing innovative products, services, job creation, facilitating technology transfer from lab to land, increasing competitiveness and enabling social empowerment (Ács et al., 2014; Bosma et al., 2018; Fayolle et al., 2016). Therefore, policymakers across the globe are emphasizing on numerous entrepreneurship support measures (Gurol & Atsan, 2006). Entrepreneurs are considered as the backbone of the industries as they come up with innovative business ideas which ultimately contribute to the social and economic growth (Khan, 2014).

In the Sultanate of Oman, thousands of students graduate from universities/colleges every year, but only a few of them intend to start their own businesses (Matlay et al., 2015). This might be due to the lack of awareness and interest in entrepreneurship, especially those who are graduating. They also not aware of the fact that the Government is providing support to graduated youth to start an entrepreneurial venture and also there are companies providing support to help the student but with certain conditions conducting entrepreneurship competitions (Khan et al., 2005). Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in Oman have also

introduced entrepreneurship as a part of their curriculum to motivate the students by making it a compulsory subject as per the directive of the Ministry of Higher Education, Oman ([Bindah & Magd](#), 2016). Thus, the increase in the business knowledge of graduates and business risk understanding influences them towards entrepreneurship ([Ibrahim et al.](#), 2017). Though such entrepreneurial potentials (EP) are enhanced the rate of entrepreneurial ventures is very low. An individual with EP is one who bears risks, works under uncertainty, combines and manages capital, innovates on all fronts on regular basis, and is motivated by business results ([Krueger & Brazeal](#), 1994, [Sahay & Rai](#), 2004).

Thus, it has become necessary to find out the factors impeding the entrepreneurial intentions of the graduating students towards starting businesses and their knowledge and creativity towards entrepreneurship. Therefore, the following research questions arise:

Research Questions

1. What are the factors impacting the Entrepreneurial Intention of graduating students?
2. How do the factors impact the Entrepreneurial intention of graduating students?

Based on the above research questions, it is defined that the objective of the study is to critically analyze the review of literature on the factors impacting the entrepreneurial intention of the graduating students and to critically analyze the impact of such factors on the entrepreneurial intention of the graduating students.

Literature Review

Entrepreneurial Potentials

Circumstances and traits have driven and continue to drive 'real-life' entrepreneurs in students who have entrepreneurial potential ([Galloway et al.](#), 2006). Entrepreneurial potential (EP) is a measure of individual capability and desire to become an entrepreneur and is recognized as an important precursor to entrepreneurial events or activities ([Krueger & Brazeal](#), 1994). Entrepreneurial potential on which the two groups differed was their predisposition to risk-taking. Females were less disposed to taking risks and it is not true that the female student in middle-east countries may be less averse to entrepreneurial activities ([Zeffane](#), 2013). The classification of idea factors will identify the go or no-go decision for a new entrepreneur and the selection process for a business based on their personality traits and preferences ([Wong et al.](#), 2005). The personality traits of students indirectly influence their intentions to start a new business through their attitudes ([Lüthje and Franke](#), 2003). Young students are ambitious and energetic, and love to venture into entrepreneurial businesses by providing what is new, useful – innovation ([Haddad et al.](#), 2019). Undergraduate students have a high level of potential to become entrepreneurs and they are considered as the source of potential entrepreneurs ([Postigo et al.](#), 2003). As Engineering students reported to have many enterprise skills, many of them aim to start firms as they understand the enterprise skills which are relevant to employment and personal development ([Galloway et al.](#), 2006).

Government Support

The Government has an important role to play in changing the attitude of graduates towards entrepreneurship and setting effective entrepreneurship strategies ([Ibrahim et al.](#), 2017). In an attempt to diversify the economy and stimulate private enterprise development, government agencies and private institutions are participating in different entrepreneurship development activities ([Khan & Al Moharby](#), 2007). Considering the importance of entrepreneurship in the growth of countries, the Government of Oman is trying entrepreneurship education towards people who have an entrepreneurial mind ([Yarahmadi & Magd](#), 2016). Students are not aware of whether Government support to start a business is available in Oman ([Varghese & Hassan](#), 2012). Indeed, Government support is extended in Oman through the ministries across a range of government bodies from labor to technology and education to industrial development ([Ennis](#), 2015). Big merchant families also back Government support by playing key roles in Oman's Chamber of Commerce ([Valeri](#), 2013).

Creativity

Creativity adds excellence and enhances the capability of students toward creative thinking and creativity is seen as a behavior that generates useful ideas for the development ([Mathisen et al.](#), 2012). Entrepreneurs determine their future themselves and go into the battlefield of work and planning towards job creation ([Hamdan](#), 2019). The central role of creativity and innovation in entrepreneurship is in the generation of new ideas which has commercial and social value ([Matriano & Suguku](#), 2015). Crowdfunding has a role in boosting the entrepreneurial creativity of university students and the business incubators at universities promote creative innovation, by providing support for their transformation into projects through crowdfunding ([El Talla et al.](#), 2018). The educational system, in Oman, has been accused of not encouraging

innovation and creativity, but rather promoting memorizing and imitating (Al-Shanfari, 2012). The culture of creativity depends on many factors such as structural characteristics, personality traits, and management practices (Yilmaz, 2010). The perception of the relationship between the person and the environment and creativity is conditioned by the personality traits and the different perceptions of the surrounding world (Durrah, et al., 2018; Sokol et al., 2015).

Education

Education and new venture creation are positively and significantly correlated (Hunjira et al., 2011). There is a relationship between the individuals’ educational level and their probability of becoming entrepreneurs (Cowling and Taylor, 2001; Delmar and Davidsson, 2000). The role of higher education is essential to develop the entrepreneurial potential and the academic environment may be useful to foster a more favorable atmosphere for innovation and entrepreneurship (Marques & Moreira, 2013). The long-term view of the entrepreneurial potential of graduate entrepreneurship is only feasible as new graduates lack the resources, skills, and experience necessary for sustainability and growth of ventures (Galloway & Brown, 2002).

Hypotheses

Based on the above review of literature, the independent variables considered are Entrepreneurial Potential, Government support, Creativity, and Education. Thus, the following hypotheses were derived:

1. Entrepreneurial Potential influences the entrepreneurial intention of the students
2. Government support impacts the entrepreneurial intention of the students
3. Creativity influences the entrepreneurial intention of the students
4. Education impact the entrepreneurial intention of the students.

Research Methodology

The research work was done to study the entrepreneurial intentions of graduating students at Sohar University. 269 undergraduate students were selected on a random sampling basis from Sohar University and were considered to be the sample for the study. An online questionnaire was shared through digital media for survey purposes which were filled by students. The statistical analysis was carried out using excel and SPSS.

Findings

Table.1 Reliability Analysis

	N	%
Valid Cases	269	100.0
Excluded	0	0.0

Cronbach's Alpha	No. of Items
.953	35

The reliability analysis shows that the Cronbach Alpha score = 0.953 > 0.7

Table 2 Demographic Details

		Frequency	%
Gender	Male	215	79.9%
	Female	54	20.1%
Age	20- <25	196	72.9%
	25- <30	44	16.4%
	30-<35	20	7.4%
	30 above	9	3.3%
Working status	Working	74	27.5%
	Not working	195	72.5%
Want to establish new business	Yes	194	72.1%
	No	75	27.9%
Willing to give up jobs	Yes	167	62.1%
	No	102	37.9%

Entrepreneurs in family	Yes	179	66.5%
	No	90	33.5%
Have the confidence to start a business	Yes	173	64.3%
	No	96	35.7%
The main reason for starting their own business	The success story of entrepreneurs	50	18.6%
	Trg & dev. opportunities	70	26.0%
	Financial support	53	19.7%
	Family support	52	19.3%

Source: Questionnaire

Table.3 Entrepreneurial Potentials

Statements	SA	A	N	D	SD	K-S value	χ^2	p-value
The graduate has skills in building relationships with others	37 13.8%	94 34.9%	94 34.9%	18 6.7%	26 9.7%	.207	140.216	.000
The graduate has the skills to take responsibility	52 19.3%	105 39.0%	63 23.4%	30 11.2%	19 7.1%	.246		
The necessary knowledge was acquired to meet the labour market needs	41 15.2%	86 32.0%	87 32.3%	38 14.1%	17 6.3%	.194		
The graduate has effective communication skills	49 18.2%	104 38.7%	77 28.6%	27 10.0%	12 4.5%	.232		
I prefer to overcome challenges than to create new opportunities	50 18.6%	97 36.1%	78 29.0%	26 9.7%	18 6.7%	.220		
The graduate can accomplish several tasks	65 24.2%	99 36.8%	68 25.3%	19 7.1%	18 6.7%	.233		
The graduates have the confidence to start a business	60 22.3%	112 41.6%	57 21.2%	22 8.2%	18 6.7%	.264		

Null Hypotheses.1: There is no relationship between the choice of the respondents and the Graduates Potentials.

From table No.3, it is observed that the p-value is less than 0.05 which means that the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a clear relationship between the choices of the respondents and the Graduates Potentials. Comparing the K-S values that were obtained from the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, it can be observed that 'The graduates have the confidence to start a business' ranked first (.264), followed by, 'The graduate has the skills to take responsibility' (.246), and 'The graduate can accomplish several tasks' (.233).

Table.4 Government Support

Statements	SA	A	N	D	SD	K-S Value	χ^2	p-value
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Help from the Government encourages starting a business	70 26.0%	84 31.2%	72 26.8%	26 9.7%	17 6.3%	.205	241.333	.000
Project control by the Government since its beginning makes the project successful	57 21.2%	101 37.5%	76 28.3%	22 8.2%	13 4.8%	.227		
New ideas by students need Government support to put into use	88 32.7%	109 40.5%	46 17.1%	11 4.1%	15 5.6%	.267		
Emotional support from family and friends makes proud	120 44.6%	76 28.3%	54 20.1%	8 3.0%	11 4.1%	.257		
I am sure the Government will support to start a project	41 15.2%	85 31.6%	85 31.6%	41 15.2%	17 6.3%	.193		
Government supports projects to grow	47 17.5%	107 39.8%	85 31.6%	15 5.6%	15 5.6%	.232		
The government encourages graduates to become entrepreneurs	44 16.4%	97 36.1%	85 31.6%	23 8.6%	18 6.7%	.216		

Null Hypotheses.2: There is no relationship between the choice of the respondents and the Government support.

From table No.4, it is observed that the p-value is less than 0.05 which means that the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a clear relationship between the choices of the respondents and the Government support. Comparing the K-S values that were obtained from the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, it can be observed that ‘New ideas by students need Government support to put into use’ ranked first (.267), followed by, ‘Emotional support from family and friends makes proud’ (.257), and ‘Government supports projects to grow’ (.232).

Table.5 Creativity

Statements	SA	A	N	D	SD	K-S value	χ^2	p-value
I can do business in a new & interesting way	43 16.0%	123 45.7%	70 26.0%	20 7.4%	13 4.8%	.270	187.963	.000
The products should be different and better	105 39.0%	102 37.9%	33 12.3%	15 5.6%	12 4.5%	.267		
Creativity is essential for a new business	109 40.5%	99 36.8%	35 13.0%	17 6.3%	9 3.3%	.255		
I have creative talents to become an entrepreneur	66 24.5%	117 43.5%	61 22.7%	14 5.2%	11 4.1%	.262		
My creative skills encourages me to engage in entrepreneurship	52 19.3%	120 44.6%	74 27.5%	15 5.6%	8 3.0%	.258		
I have the ability to present ideas	65 24.2%	127 47.2%	57 21.2%	11 4.1%	9 3.3%	.278		
I can find solutions to problems	67 24.9%	123 45.7%	53 19.7%	13 4.8%	13 4.8%	.280		

Null Hypotheses.3: There is no relationship between the choice of the respondents and Creativity.

From table No.5, it is observed that the p-value is less than 0.05 which means that the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a clear relationship between the choices of the respondents and Creativity. Comparing the K-S values that were obtained from the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, it can be observed that ‘I can find solutions to problems’ ranked first (.280), followed by, ‘I can present ideas’ (.278), and ‘I can do business in a new & interesting way’ (.270).

Table.6 Education

Statements	SA	A	N	D	SD	K-S value	χ^2	P-value
Entrepreneurship education gives students business knowledge and a better understanding	65 24.2%	111 41.3%	58 21.6%	22 8.2%	13 4.8%	.258	204.253	.000
Working in a small business makes students gain real experience	76 28.3%	110 40.9%	60 22.3%	11 4.1%	12 4.5%	.252		
Entrepreneurship education competitions inspires and motivates	78 29.0%	92 34.2%	67 24.9%	19 7.1%	13 4.8%	.221		
Students attending entrepreneurial competitions needs emotional support	93 34.6%	102 37.9%	53 19.7%	11 4.1%	10 3.7%	.242		
Entrepreneurial activities increased my leadership qualities	58 21.6%	108 40.1%	73 27.1%	19 7.1%	11 4.1%	.240		
Entrepreneurial education motivates students to start a business	60 22.3%	113 42.0%	60 22.3%	22 8.2%	14 5.2%	.261		
I have gained lots of business knowledge	47 17.5%	112 41.6%	85 31.6%	14 5.2%	11 4.1%	.239		

Null Hypotheses.4: There is no relationship between the choice of the respondents and Education.

From table No.6, it is observed that the p-value is less than 0.05 which means that the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a clear relationship between the choices of the respondents and the Education. Comparing the K-S values that were obtained from the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, it can be observed that 'Entrepreneurial education motivates students to start a business' ranked first (.261), followed by, 'Entrepreneurship education gives students business knowledge and better understanding' (.258), and 'Working in small business makes students gain real experience' (.252).

Table.7 Entrepreneurial intentions

Statements	SA	A	N	D	SD	K-S value	χ^2	P-value
The graduates have the intention to start a business	46 17.1%	105 39.0%	83 39.9%	20 7.4%	15 5.6%	.230	183.684	.000
I would like to become a successful businessman /women in the future	100 37.2%	98 36.4%	48 17.8%	11 4.1%	12 4.5%	.244		
I intend to obtain a social status as an entrepreneur	87 32.3%	91 33.8%	64 23.8%	15 5.6%	12 4.5%	.221		
I have a desire to start entrepreneurial activities	69 25.7%	103 38.3%	74 27.5%	12 4.5%	11 4.1%	.229		
I would like to create my own business	98 36.4%	84 31.2%	58 21.6%	19 7.1%	10 3.7%	.215		
I would like to implement a new business idea	76 28.3%	104 38.7%	62 23.0%	13 4.8%	14 5.2%	.244		
I can successfully implement the entrepreneurial process	64 23.8%	104 38.7%	59 21.9%	26 9.7%	16 5.9%	.248		

Null Hypotheses.5: There is no relationship between the choice of the respondents and the Entrepreneurial Intention.

From table No.7, it is observed that the p-value is less than 0.05 which means that the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a clear relationship between the choices of the respondents and the Entrepreneurial Intention. Comparing the K-S values that were obtained from the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, it can be observed that 'I can successfully implement the entrepreneurial process' ranked first (.248), followed by, 'I would like to implement a new business idea' & 'I would like to become a successful businessman/women in the future' (.244), and 'The graduates have the intention to start a business' (.230).

Table 8. (a), (b), (c) and (d) Regression

Variables Entered/Removed^a

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	Education, Entrepreneurial Potentials, Government Support, Creativity ^b	...	Enter

^a Dependent variable: Entrepreneurial Intention

^b All requested variables entered

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of Estimate
1	.727 ^a	.529	.522	3.78306

^a Predictors: (Constant), Education, Entrepreneurial Potentials, Government Support, Creativity

ANOVA^a

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	4178.185	4	1044.546	72.986	.000 ^b
Residual	3721.000	260	14.312		
Total	7899.185	264			

^a Dependent variable: Entrepreneurial Intention

^b Predictors: (Constant), Education, Entrepreneurial Potentials, Government Support, Creativity

Coefficients^a

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	4.676	1.362		3.433	.001
Entrepreneurial Potentials	.134	.063	.138	2.138	.033
Government Support Creativity	.088	.076	.077	1.154	.249
Education	.373	.076	.352	4.915	.000
	.240	.075	.242	3.218	.001

^a Dependent variable: Entrepreneurial Intention

From the above co-efficient table, it can be seen that the p-value of Government support is > .05. Therefore, eliminating the variable government support, the linear regression analysis is done again and we get the results as follows:

Table 9. (a), (b), (c) and (d) Regression

Variables Entered/Removed^a

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	Education, Entrepreneurial Potentials, Creativity ^b	...	Enter

^a Dependent variable: Entrepreneurial Intention

^b All requested variables entered

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of Estimate
1	.731 ^a	.535	.529	3.89009

^a Predictors: (Constant), Education, Entrepreneurial Potentials, Government Support, Creativity

ANOVA^a

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	4560.722	3	1523.541	100.678	.000 ^b
Residual	3979.918	263	15.133		
Total	8550.540	266			

^a Dependent variable: Entrepreneurial Intention

^b Predictors: (Constant), Education, Entrepreneurial Potentials, Government Support, Creativity

Coefficients^a

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	4.486	1.289		3.481	.001
Entrepreneurial Potentials	.142	.061	.142	2.313	.021
Creativity	.439	.075	.406	5.819	.000
Education	.256	.071	.253	3.620	.000

^a Dependent variable: Entrepreneurial Intention

The R² value of .535 shows that 53.5 % of the samples are influenced by the linear regression. From F-table, it is clear that the p-value is .000 < .05 which confirms that there is a linear relationship between the dependent and independent variables. Therefore, the obtained linear regression is as follows:

$$EI = 4.486 + .142 EP + .439 C + .256 E$$

Where EI is the Entrepreneurial Intention, EP is the Entrepreneurial Potentials, C is the Creativity and E is the Education.

Thus, it can be seen that the Entrepreneurial intention is influenced by the Graduate Potentials, Creativity, and Education of the students and not by the Government support. i.e. the claimed hypothesis is proved.

Discussion

Most of the respondents (72.1%) wants to establish new businesses. 64.3% of them responded that they are confident in starting their own businesses. The main reason for their intention to start the new businesses was the training and development opportunities (26%), followed by their expectation of financial support (19.7%) and expected friends support (19.3%) in establishing new businesses.

Among the graduate potentials, it was found that most of the graduates have the confidence to start a business and they also believed that the graduates have the skills to take responsibility, and the ability to accomplish several tasks.

Among the Government support factors, it was found that most of the students believed that new ideas of the students need Government support to put into use and emotional support from family and friends makes them feel proud.

Among the creativity factors, most of them believed that the students can find solutions to problems and have the ability to present ideas, and can do business in a new innovative way.

Among the educational factors, the majority of the students believed that entrepreneurship education motivates the students to start a business as it gives knowledge and a better understanding of business, and working in small businesses makes the students gain real-life experience.

Among the entrepreneurial intention factors, most of the students believed that they can successfully implement the entrepreneurial process as they would like to implement a new business idea and they would like to become successful businessmen/women in the future.

It was proved that Graduate Potentials, Creativity, and Education impacts the Entrepreneurial Intention of the students but not the Government support i.e. Entrepreneurial intention is influenced by Graduate Potentials, Creativity, and Education of the students.

Conclusion

Entrepreneurship is an increasingly popular feature of modern society today. Entrepreneurship seeds in students the qualities like creativity, self-confidence, ambition, and the ability to take risks. The study confirms that undergraduate students are developing creative skills and bringing out their entrepreneurial potentials and improvising their practical knowledge through their education which is in line with the findings by [Khan \(2008\)](#). These qualities help to develop society and keep pace with the development and technological changes in the environment through entrepreneurial intention among the students. Indeed, the motivation for the student to achieve their dreams comes up with their ideas taught by the teachers educating courses like entrepreneurship education and the expected support from the educational authorities and government which is similar to the findings of [Al Buraiki and Khan \(2018\)](#). They create opportunities to satisfy the needs of individuals through establishing new markets and are creative in promoting innovative methods.

Suggestions

The current study is concerned with entrepreneurship for students who are about to graduate. Hence, the following suggestions are made:

1. The main focus of the graduating students should be towards creativity encompassing innovation and practical usage so that the realm of entrepreneurship emerges out.
2. The graduating students developing creative skills and enhancing their entrepreneurial potential through their collegiate education whereas they need proper guidance to fulfill their entrepreneurial intention which is in the hands of teachers.
3. Students should be exposed to the development of various skills – creativity, communication, presentation, marketing, funds management, etc.
4. Graduating students should be invited to a platform where competitions of all innovative kinds should be conducted regularly and the participants should be guided with assistance to improve their ideas.
5. Business knowledge with more focus on practical experience should be initiated rather than sharing simply theoretical knowledge.
6. The government should encourage students through various schemes so that the graduate students will come forward to take up new ventures with their innovative ideas.

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